

Generative AI: Transformative Applications Across Diverse Domains

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Abstract

This article examines how large-scale generative AI models, including multimodal (LMMs) and language models (LLMs), are transforming various industries. In manufacturing, LMMs help detect defects, adding interpretability, but often require specialized models for accuracy. In healthcare, LLMs enhance datasets for rare diseases, improving classification through high quality data augmentation. Generative AI also supports synthetic image generation, enriching datasets. Within gaming, LLMs enable interactive avatars for richer user experiences. In reinforcement learning, LLMs provide affordable demonstrations for complex tasks, especially in the early stages. Each application highlights the strengths and limits of generative AI and the considerations for achieving optimal results.

Keywords: generative AI, LMM, LLM, anomaly detection, data augmentation, clinical notes, serious games, reinforcement learning

1. Introduction

The landscape of artificial intelligence is undergoing a revolutionary transformation driven by the unprecedented capabilities of generative AI. In particular, large multimodal and language models (LMMs and LLMs) [1, 2] are breaking traditional boundaries, demonstrating remarkable abilities to process, interpret, and synthesize data across multiple media types, including text, images, and speech [3]. Unlike traditional AI systems that primarily process and analyze existing data [4], generative AI is capable of creating

entirely new content. By leveraging large datasets and sophisticated architectures, these models can produce diverse and innovative outputs [3], propelling AI from a tool of analysis to one of creation.

The foundations of generative AI can be traced to academic research conducted in the 1950s. A significant milestone was achieved in the early 1970s when a program designed to create and exhibit computer-generated paintings, was developed [5]. Throughout the following decades, generative planning systems were developed through the implementation of symbolic AI techniques, including state space search and constraint satisfaction [6], which were used to generate sequences of actions to reach a specified goal.

A paradigm shift occurred when deep learning gained prominence, and the focus was redirected toward discriminative models for image classification and speech recognition tasks [7]. The field was subsequently transformed due to the introduction of generative models, specifically variational autoencoders and generative adversarial networks (GANs) [8], which enabled neural networks to be utilized for the production of complex, novel outputs rather than simple predictions.

The development trajectory was further accelerated by the introduction of the Transformer network [9], through which generative model performance was enhanced beyond the capabilities of traditional recurrent structures, such as Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) networks [10, 11]. This advancement facilitated the creation of GPT-1 [12], followed by the more sophisticated GPT-2 [13], wherein impressive capabilities in unsupervised learning and task generalization were demonstrated. These models were distinguished by their utilization of unsupervised and semi-supervised learning approaches, thereby reducing the dependence on human-labeled data and enabling the training of more extensive networks.

Recent developments in the field have been characterized by widespread generative AI proliferation, as evidenced by the deployment of systems such as DALL-E [14], Midjourney, and Stable Diffusion [15], through which high-quality art can be generated from text prompts. The public availability of ChatGPT popularized the use of generative AI for general-purpose text-based tasks. Following this advancement, the release of GPT-4 has prompted scholarly discourse regarding its classification as an early form of Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), although consensus regarding its proximity to human-level intelligence remains unestablished [16]. The evolution of the field has been demonstrated through the introduction of ImageBind, whereby multi-modal integration of text, images, video, and audio data has been achieved

[17].

This article examines how powerful AI tools are being used across various fields to increase efficiency, improve accuracy, and enhance user engagement. It presents a series of use cases, each highlighting a specific problem within a particular field. In the field of industrial anomaly detection [18], we examine the efficacy of generalist LLMs in identifying defects and compare them to specialized models. For clinical data augmentation [19], large models are employed to balance datasets for better disease classification accuracy, particularly with infrequent conditions. In synthetic image generation [20], we explore how Generative AI can supplement datasets with diverse image samples to train more effective algorithms. Furthermore, in serious gaming, the integration of LLM-driven conversational agents could empower new scenarios for emerging interactive narratives [21]. Lastly, we address the role of LLMs in Reinforcement Learning (RL) and Imitation Learning (IL), where their capacity to generate automated demonstrations provides cost-effective solutions [22]. This examination reveals both the challenges and advantages of deploying generative AI models, underscoring their adaptability and transformative potential across fields.

Each use case includes an introduction tailored to its specific domain, a work description, and a conclusion. The overall structure of this article is organized as follows:

- Industrial anomaly detection is discussed in Section 2.
- Data augmentation for clinical notes is covered in Section 3.
- Data augmentation for images is detailed in Section 4.
- Engagement and UX in serious games is described in Section 5.
- Demonstrations in RL/IL are showcased in Section 6.

Finally, Section 7 synthesizes the individual conclusions from the previous sections into an overall summary.

2. Industrial Anomaly Detection

2.1. Introduction

Unsupervised anomaly detection in images encompasses a wide range of methods, with numerous approaches proposed to address this challenge [23].

A successful approach is the student-teacher (S-T) framework, where a student network is trained to mimic the output of a pretrained, frozen CNN teacher [24]. Another method is to use Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [8] to model the manifold of the training data using a GAN [25] trained solely on defect-free images. The generator produces realistic-looking images that fool a simultaneously trained discriminator. Convolutional Autoencoders (CAEs) [26] are also commonly used for unsupervised anomaly detection. They attempt to reconstruct defect-free training samples through a bottleneck (latent space). During testing, they fail to accurately reproduce images that differ from the training data, allowing anomalies to be detected by comparing the input to its reconstruction. Extensions to CAEs include Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) [27], which have been used among other solutions for unsupervised segmentation of anomalies in brain MRI scans. In addition to learning representations from the training data, some methods leverage features extracted from pre-trained Convolutional Neural Networks. Traditional approaches are also still employed. For example, the extraction of hand-crafted features from defect-free texture images and a model of their distribution using a Gaussian Mixture Model is used to detect anomalies [28], though their method is limited to regular textures.

The introduction of the MVTec AD dataset [29] has accelerated the development of methods for industrial applications [18], where the goal is to detect anomalies in images containing only normal, defect-free examples during training. Recently, several new industrial anomaly detection datasets have been introduced, such as the Visual Anomaly (VisA) dataset [30] and the MVTec Logical Constraints (MVTec LOCO) dataset [31], which contain more challenging anomalies than MVTec AD.

This use case focuses on researching solutions for the problem of detecting defects in objects using large multimodal models (LMM) or visual language models (VLM). An evaluation of different models and prompts is conducted on two object anomaly detection datasets to validate the experiment. Additionally, the advantages and disadvantages of each technique, such as processing speed, response quality, and explanation of the results, are discussed.

2.2. Datasets

The experimental evaluation was conducted using two distinct databases for anomaly detection: the publicly available MVTecAD dataset and the WoodAD dataset.

2.2.1. *MVTecAD*

The MVTEC database MVTEC Anomaly Detection Dataset is a dataset designed to evaluate anomaly detection methods with a focus on industrial inspection [29, 32]. It contains more than 5000 images divided into fifteen categories of objects and textures. Each category includes a set with various types of defects and defect-free images.

2.2.2. *WoodAD*

Experiments were also conducted with the Wood Anomaly Detection database created by Instituto Tecnológico de Informática (ITI). It contains images of wooden objects with various types of defects: porosity, stains, knots, cracks and also defect-free images (see Figure 1). It has a total of 802 training images and 2398 test images, but due to the difficulty encountered in anomaly detection with traditional methods, two test subsets were created for better evaluation. A simple dataset called *test_easy* (12 images), and a medium difficulty dataset (*test_medium*) with 148 images.

Figure 1: Examples from the WoodAD database. Different types of defects are shown: porosity, knot, stains, cracks.

2.3. *Models*

Two different LLM's have been explored. GPT-4o, which is able to process both text and visual content, and Gemini 1.5 Flash, which is designed for low-latency applications.

2.3.1. GPT-4o

GPT-4o (“o” for “omni”) developed by OpenAI, is a multimodal model that is capable of understanding and generating text in a coherent and relevant manner, and it has introduced the ability to process multimodal inputs, such as images, allowing it to generate descriptions and responses based on visual content.

2.3.2. Gemini 1.5 Flash

Gemini 1.5 Flash is the latest version released by Google from the Gemini family of artificial intelligence models, presented in May 2024. It is a lightweight, fast, and efficient model, the fastest version of Gemini 1.5 developed to date. This model has been optimized to provide faster and more efficient responses, designed for applications where latency is important.

2.4. Prompts

For the initial tests, the GPT-4o model was used, and four different input prompts were established. Prompts 1 and 2 use only the defective image as input, while prompts 3 and 4, in addition to the image to be evaluated, show the model an example of a normal image. In these four prompts, it was indicated that the output should be 0 (normal) or 1 (defective). In all prompts, it is explicitly stated to the model that the image corresponds to a specific type of object (<OBJECT>), and in prompt 4, the list of possible defects for that specific object was also included.

Prompt 1:

The image given shows a <OBJECT>. Determine if the object contains anomalies or defects. If yes, give a specific reason.

Prompt 2:

The image given shows a <OBJECT>. Determine if the object contains anomalies or defects. If yes, give a specific reason. Normally, the given image should depict a clear and identifiable <OBJECT>, which may have defects such as broken parts, contaminations, or any other irregularity.

Prompt 3:

The first image given shows a <OBJECT> that is normal. Determine if the second image that also shows a <OBJECT> contains anomalies or defects. If yes, give a specific reason. Normally, the image given should depict a clear

and identifiable *<OBJECT>*, which may have defects such as broken parts, contaminations, or any other irregularity.

Prompt 4:

*The first image given shows a *<OBJECT>* that is normal. Determine if the second image that also shows a *<OBJECT>* contains anomalies or defects. If yes, give a specific reason. Normally, the image given should depict a clear and identifiable *<OBJECT>*, which may have defects such as *<DEFECTS>*, contaminations, or any other irregularity.*

All prompts include the following text to indicate the response format to the model:

Your answer should contain 2 parts:

"reasoning": a string that describes what you think about the given image;

"correctness": an integer, 0 if there is no anomaly in the image, 1 if it is, no partial credit;

Output example: {"reasoning": "a string", "correctness": integer, 0 or 1}.

Your response must be a valid JSON string starting with { and ending with }.

2.5. Evaluation

The results for each of the prompts and for each of the objects in the MVTecAD database, as well as the WoodAD database, are shown in Table 1. For each case, the F1 score at the image level is displayed, considering that the tested model only returns a binary output indicating whether the object has a defect or not.

The results of this initial evaluation help us identify the most effective prompt and refine it to ensure the model returns optimal results. According to Table 1, prompt 3 yields the best overall performance. However, when considering only the MVTec dataset, prompt 2 performs best, while prompt 4 achieves the highest performance for the WoodAD dataset. This behavior may be due to the distinct characteristics of each dataset and the semantics of the prompts. For instance, the WoodAD dataset includes a wider variety of defects such as porosity, knots, stains, and cracks, whereas the MVTec dataset primarily features broken or contaminated objects. Thus, prompt 4 has an advantage as it accommodates a broader range of defects represented by *<DEFECTS>*.

Table 1: F1 scores for the four prompts initially tested with the GPT-4o model

Dataset	Class	Prompt 1	Prompt 2	Prompt 3	Prompt 4
MVTec	Bottle	0.855	0.861	0.913	0.913
	Cable	0.818	0.827	0.770	0.783
	Capsule	0.946	0.900	0.965	0.916
	Carpet	0.994	1.000	0.967	0.962
	Grid	1.000	1.000	0.877	0.877
	Hazelnut	0.986	0.993	0.875	0.859
	Leather	0.989	0.995	0.984	0.984
	Metal nut	0.881	0.871	0.906	0.906
	Pill	0.918	0.911	0.962	0.949
	Screw	0.847	0.886	0.874	0.856
	Tile	0.988	0.970	0.982	0.939
	Toothbrush	0.833	0.845	0.845	0.833
	Transistor	0.567	0.645	0.606	0.576
Wood	0.959	0.975	0.930	0.923	
Zipper	0.901	0.867	0.950	0.955	
WoodAD	Easy	0.857	0.737	0.900	0.952
	Medium	0.758	0.620	0.900	0.919
Average		0.888	0.877	0.894	0.888

It is also worth mentioning that including a nominal example image can sometimes lead the model to directly compare the input image with the example, resulting in false positives. Examples of this are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2: Example of a result with prompt 3. On the left, you can see the good example passed to the model, while on the right, the object to be evaluated, which is also good. However, the GPT-4o model indicates that the object is defective, stating that the 500 print is misaligned compared to the example image.

Figure 3: Example of a result with prompt 4 on WoodAD. On the left, you can see the example of a good sample passed to the model, while on the right, the object to be evaluated, which is also good. However, the GPT-4 model indicates that the piece is defective, indicating that there is a crack on the surface.

According to the previous results, the prompts have been readjusted to better indicate to the model the characteristics of the object to be evaluated. For example, the objects can be rotated or at different angles than the one shown in the example. To improve the results, tests have been conducted with two other prompts shown below, one with an image and the other with two images, including the reference sample.

Prompt 5:

The image given shows a <OBJECT>. Determine if the object contains anomalies or defects such as <DEFECTS>, contaminations, or any other irregularity. If yes, give a specific reason.

Prompt 6:

The first image given shows an example of a normal <OBJECT>. The second image also shows a <OBJECT> like the first one but not necessarily identical. It may be rotated or in a different angle/position respect to the first image. The second image can be normal or may have defects, such as <DEFECTS>, contaminations, or any other irregularity. Determine if the <OBJECT> shown in the second image contains anomalies or defects. If yes, give a specific reason.

As seen in Table 2, the results obtained with these modified prompts are much better, even for prompt 5, which uses a single input image. Finally, we chose prompt 6, which achieves the best results, and we used this prompt to test other models.

2.6. Comparison with the state-of-the-art

The EfficientAD model [33] is the state-of-the-art in anomaly detection in industrial parts, primarily evaluated on the MVTeC database. Table 3 shows a comparison of the EfficientAD model with the tested VLM models (using prompt 6).

According to Table 3, it is concluded that while the VLM models generally achieve good results, they do not reach the performance of one of state-of-the-art models for this type of task. It should also be noted that the EfficientAD model returns an error map of the piece, so it is possible to determine not only if the piece has a defect but also its location. The tests conducted with the VLM models only indicate whether the piece has a defect or not, with the advantage that they offer reasoning about what was found in the

Table 2: F1 scores obtained with the GPT-4o model for the two modified prompts

Dataset	Class	Prompt 5	Prompt 6
MVTec	Bottle	0.875	0.955
	Cable	0.869	0.864
	Capsule	0.931	0.947
	Carpet	1.000	0.983
	Grid	0.983	0.919
	Hazelnut	0.966	0.848
	Leather	0.979	0.929
	Metal nut	0.881	0.925
	Pill	0.912	0.962
	Screw	0.864	0.877
	Tile	0.970	0.955
	Toothbrush	0.857	0.857
	Transistor	0.551	0.593
Wood	0.938	0.909	
Zipper	0.881	0.951	
WoodAD	Easy	0.952	0.952
	Medium	0.880	0.930
Average		0.899	0.903

image, something that conventional models do not do. Additionally, the execution time of EfficientAD is much shorter compared to the VLM models, as observed in Table 4.

2.7. Conclusion

The VLM models used in these experiments achieve good results but do not surpass those obtained by a model specifically designed for anomaly detection like EfficientAD. However, the VLM models have the advantage of offering reasoning about what was found in the piece. Therefore, to leverage VLM models for this type of task, the ideal approach would be to combine the use of specific models for defect detection and localization with the natural language model to obtain an informed reasoning about the detected defect.

Table 3: F1 scores for the state-of-the-art model (EfficientAD-S) and the VLM models tested using prompt 6

Dataset	Class	EfficientAD-S	GPT-4o	Gemini-1.5_flash
MVTec	Bottle	1.000	0.955	0.923
	Cable	0.907	0.864	0.714
	Capsule	0.956	0.947	0.810
	Carpet	0.966	0.983	0.967
	Grid	1.000	0.919	0.898
	Hazelnut	0.897	0.848	0.952
	Leather	0.995	0.929	0.968
	Metal nut	0.978	0.925	0.875
	Pill	0.982	0.962	0.859
	Screw	0.944	0.877	0.796
	Tile	1.000	0.955	0.888
	Toothbrush	0.984	0.857	0.833
	Transistor	0.988	0.593	0.571
	Wood	0.975	0.909	0.960
Zipper	0.983	0.951	0.847	
WoodAD	Easy	1.000	0.952	0.952
	Medium	0.969	0.930	0.742
Average		0.972	0.903	0.856

Table 4: Average execution times for each model

Model	Image inference time
EfficientAD-S	0.033 s
GPT-40 (1 image)	2.81 s
GPT-40 (2 images)	3.76 s
Gemini-1.5_flash (2 images)	3.11 s

3. High Quality Contextual Data Augmentation in Clinical Notes

3.1. Introduction

Clinical notes have become a valuable source of unstructured information in the healthcare landscape. This type of data can aid in various health-related issues, including knowledge discovery, classification, risk estimation,

and decision-making. Moreover, leveraging this information in innovative ways could create new insights when combined with more traditional data sources to address diverse challenges.

In this context, [19] investigates how a large language model (LLM) trained on electronic health record (EHR) notes can enhance multiple tasks, emphasizing the importance of understanding EHR narrative elements to develop human-centered LLMs. Additionally, [34] underscores the application of LLMs across various healthcare functions. Meanwhile, [35] examines both the potential and challenges of integrating LLMs into healthcare tasks, specifically focusing on clinical notes for predictive modeling.

In clinical notes, textual data related to infrequent diseases can be overshadowed by more common diseases during AI model estimation, often leading to misclassification. To prevent this, increasing the weight of infrequent diseases becomes necessary. This adjustment can be applied at either the input or output level. One way to increase the input weight is by introducing new, high-quality textual samples for the infrequent disease.

This use case focuses on generating high-quality contextual data augmentation from original text sources to boost the number of examples for the underrepresented disease. Initially, human supervision is used to ensure the quality of augmented text. An application will display the original and generated sentences, highlighting their differences. Both qualitative and quantitative measures will be used to help users make informed decisions about the quality of the newly generated sentences.

3.2. Clinical note structure

The structure of a clinical note is composed of the following parts:

- **Reason for consultation** is the primary issue or concern that leads a patient to seek medical attention, such as a symptom or health problem. It guides the evaluation by the healthcare provider and is typically noted at the start of a consultation. An example of this could be *Acute abdominal pain in the right lower quadrant, with nausea and vomiting.*
- **Physical examination** is a healthcare provider’s assessment of a patient’s body to check overall health and detect any medical conditions. It involves techniques like inspection, palpation, percussion, and auscultation, focusing on areas based on the patient’s symptoms. For example *Pain on palpation in the right lower quadrant, without signs of peritonitis.*

- **Treatment plan** is a strategy to address a patient’s medical condition. It includes the diagnosis, specific goals, recommended interventions (such as medications and therapies), follow-up plans, and patient education. The plan serves as a roadmap for managing the patient’s health and ensures effective communication among the healthcare team, this could serve as an example *blood analysis and abdominal ultrasound. Fasting. Analgesic and antiemetics as needed. Prepare for possible surgery.*
- **Diagnosis** is the clinical determination of a disease or condition based on the synthesis of patient history, physical examination findings, and results from diagnostic tests, a diagnosis could be *Appendicitis.*

3.3. Prompt

Prompt 1:

[INST]

*First and very important, reset the previous context. Then generate **XXNUMBERXX**, keeping the context of the following original paragraph in Spanish: **XXSENTENCEXX***

Please follow these restrictions:

- *Do not repeat the same paragraph under any circumstances.*
- *The generated sentences must have between **YYYY** and **ZZZZ** characters. In addition, evaluate each of the generated paragraphs individually with respect to the original paragraph, giving a score from 0 to 100 based on the deviation from the meaning of the original paragraph and explaining how both paragraphs vary.*
- *The output must be in JSON list format, which must contain the following fields: original, generated, score, explanation, valid, clarification.*
- *Any additional information must be put in the previously mentioned fields, explanation, clarification. It is mandatory that all output information is in complete JSON format.*

[/INST]

3.4. LLM (Large Language Model)

A Large Language Model (LLM) is a type of artificial intelligence designed to understand and generate human-like text based on vast amounts of training data. These models generate the next *token* based on the decoding method selected which is defined by the sampling parameters of which the most relevant are temperature, top-p or top-k which adjust the confidence and randomness of the generation.

1. **Temperature:** This parameter adjusts the confidence and randomness by scaling the generator model's log-likelihood. Higher temperatures are associated with more creative AI generation but come with a higher probability of generating semantically distant sentences from the original ones.
2. **Top-k:** This parameter allows obtaining only the top-k tokens with the greatest likelihood at each step.
3. **Top-p:** This parameter filters tokens whose cumulative likelihood is lower than a threshold p , including only those tokens with a likelihood above this threshold.

The application of these heterogeneous parameters follows a hierarchical approach. First, **temperature** scaling is applied to adjust the model's confidence, followed by the application of the **top-k** parameter to limit the number of potential token choices. Finally, the **top-p** parameter (nucleus sampling) refines the output by dynamically filtering the token set based on cumulative probability. In summary, the **temperature** parameter controls the level of randomness, while the **top-k** and **top-p** parameters influence the diversity and number of tokens generated. The model used in this process is briefly outlined in the following subsection.

Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1

mistralai/Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 Apache License Version 2.0, January 2004. The Mixtral-8x7B Large Language Model (LLM) is a pretrained generative Sparse Mixture of Experts (mistral.ai).

3.5. App Description

Human supervision is integrated through a web application designed to streamline the generation and validation of new sentences. The application is divided into three key sections: the first is dedicated to configuration and

prompt engineering, the second handles input sentence context for AI-based generation, and the final section is focused on human validation to ensure quality and accuracy.

Figure 4 illustrates the application’s configuration page, where the three previously mentioned decoding parameters can be adjusted. Additionally, users can specify the number of sentences to generate for each contextual sentence, as well as customize an editable template for the prompt used in generating new sentences based on the context.

AI Data Generation

Config Generation Validation

Branching

Temperature

Top-P

Top-K

Temperature

0.10 1.00

Number of sentences to generate

2 - +

Prompt

Figure 4: First step: Configuration parameters and prompt.

The next page is illustrated in Figure 5, where the system requires the user to either input a text or upload a text file from which the generation will be performed.

Finally, Figure 6 presents the generated information for human validation. In this view, we can distinguish between the original and generated sentences, with differences highlighted in color to make it easier to spot variations. Below, the automatic AI-generated explanation outlines the key differences between the original and generated sentences. Additionally, numerical values generated by the AI (left) or computed from embeddings (right) are displayed to provide objective metrics for determining the semantic equivalence between the original and generated paragraphs. The buttons allow users to navigate through different generated sentences and make decisions about whether the semantic meaning is equivalent (Right) or different (Wrong).

AI Data Generation

Config **Generation** Validation

Choose a file

Drag and drop file here
Limit 200MB per file

Browse files

Original Sentence

Acute abdominal pain in the right lower quadrant, with nausea and vomiting. Pain on palpation in the right lower quadrant, without signs of peritonitis. Blood analysis and abdominal ultrasound. Fasting. Analgesic and antiemetics as needed. Prepare for possible surgery.

Status

Generate

Figure 5: Second step: IA Generation.

3.6. Future Work

For future development, we propose the following strategies:

- **Translation to English.** To mitigate the observed performance limitations in Spanish, implementing a machine translation model to convert sentences into English may offer significant insights. This would allow for a comparative evaluation of performance between languages.
- **Iterative text generation.** Adopting an iterative approach to text generation, where new texts are produced by modifying the decoding parameters at each iteration, could enhance flexibility and creativity in the output.
- **Automated quality assessment.** Leveraging active learning techniques, models can be developed to automatically assess and classify the quality of generated sentences, improving overall output precision.
- **Domain-specific fine-tuning.** Fine-tuning models with domain-specific data can lead to more accurate sentence generation. This approach may also reduce hallucination rates and increase creative potential, en-

AI Data Generation

Config Generation **Validation**

Source Sentence

Acute abdominal pain in the right lower quadrant, with nausea and vomiting. Pain on palpation in the right lower quadrant, without signs of peritonitis. Blood analysis and abdominal ultrasound. Fasting. Analgesic and antiemetics as needed. Prepare for possible surgery.

Original sentence

Acute abdominal pain in the right lower quadrant, with nausea and vomiting. Pain on palpation in the right lower quadrant, without signs of peritonitis. Blood analysis and abdominal ultrasound. Fasting. Analgesic and antiemetics as needed. Prepare for possible surgery.

Generated sentence

Sharp abdominal pain in the lower right area, accompanied by nausea and vomiting. Tenderness upon palpation in the same region, yet no signs of peritonitis are present. Order blood work and abdominal ultrasound. Proceed with fasting. Prescribe analgesics and antiemetics as required. Prepare for potential surgical intervention.

Explanation

The generated paragraph conveys the same information as the original, using different vocabulary. Both include the symptoms of acute abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, tenderness upon palpation, and the absence of peritonitis signs. Both also mention the same diagnostic procedures and treatments, including blood analysis, abdominal ultrasound, fasting, and the administration of analgesics and antiemetics. However, the generated paragraph uses the term 'sharp' instead of 'acute', 'proceed with fasting' instead of 'fasting', and 'prescribe' instead of 'as needed'.

Evaluation

IA Validation:	Distances:
Score: 90	COS: 0.9688
Valid: Yes	L0: 4096.0
	L1: 11.51
	L2: 0.2498

First Righth Wrong

Figure 6: Third step: Validation of generated sentences.

abling the model to generate more contextually relevant and diverse texts based on the input.

3.7. Conclusion

This application provides an intuitive, graphical interface designed to seamlessly integrate human oversight into the validation process of AI-generated text, ensuring a foundational standard of contextual fidelity and semantic integrity. It serves as a foundation for semi-automatic validation systems, leveraging models that assess the quality of generated sentences, supplemented by human validation at various stages.

4. Data Augmentation for images with Generative AI

4.1. Introduction

Deep learning models often struggle with domain adaptation when exposed to new conditions. This issue is particularly evident in applications like anomaly detection, where insufficient training data can hinder the model’s ability to generalize effectively [20]. Adding more training data from diverse domains can help alleviate this issue; however, collecting high-quality and relevant data is inherently costly [36].

Significant research efforts have been dedicated to traditional data augmentation approaches based on geometric modifications, including cropping, translations, and rotations [20]. The limitations of these techniques are that the subject features may be altered and the limited image diversity. On the other hand, recent advancements within generative AI are providing new opportunities for data augmentation [20] using large language models (LLMs) [37], vision-language models (VLMs) [38], image synthesis models [39]. In particular, the ability to synthesize photorealistic images from natural language [40]. These models demonstrate exceptional performance on various tasks such as text-to-image generation [15], image-to-image modification [41], and image inpainting. Recent work shows that large-scale diffusion models can be fine-tuned to generate augmented images for improving recognition tasks [42]. While fine-tuning image generation models for data augmentation is effective, their complexity and the need for replication across diverse datasets often make it impractical. Methods for augmenting visually realistic images using text-guided techniques without model fine-tuning are proposed in [41].

The objective of this use case is to analyze different techniques for generating synthetic images to augment data sets. The purpose is to enrich the databases with new samples to improve the performance of algorithms trained on them, either due to a lack of samples or to scale the size of the model.

The plan is to evaluate the various available methods for generating synthetic images conditioned by input images (e.g., diffusion models or DMs). The database to be used is WoodAD, which consists of woodworm moths images and is presented in Section 2.2.2.

4.2. Experimentation without Ad-hoc Training

The objective of this section is to evaluate how different pre-trained algorithms perform without fine-tuning on our wood database.

4.2.1. Exploring SD Image Variations

Hugging Face¹ offers a model that can transform input images while preserving their content. The model has two parameters: inference steps, which represent the number of denoising iterations computed to infer the final image and guidance, which controls how closely the output should adhere to the model’s input. The results of adjusting these hyperparameters can be seen in Figure 7.

Our experimentation indicates that the model distorts the input image significantly, resulting in an output that bears little resemblance to the original, apart from recognizing the material as wood. Consequently, we conclude that this model is not suitable for our purposes without additional fine-tuning.

¹<https://huggingface.co/lambdalabs/sd-image-variations-diffusers>

Figure 7: Results with SD Image Variations for Inference Steps [20, 50, 100, 200] and Guidance [1, 3, 7, 10] The blacked-out cells represent images that were blocked by the model’s content filter.

4.2.2. Exploring *InstructPix2Pix*

On HuggingFace², there is an image-to-image model that allows modifying an image by providing a prompt, while maintaining the structure of the image. This could be interesting based on the results from the previous section.

This model has the same hyperparameters as the case discussed in the previous section. However, in addition to an image, this model also accepts a prompt to guide the modifications. The specific goal of this model is to generate defects on training images from the wood database, which are all

²<https://huggingface.co/timbrooks/instruct-pix2pix>

correct (or nominal images). The defects in this particular database include: porosity, knots, cracks, and paint stains.

Prompts like “Wood. Keep color. Add defects. porosity. knot. crack. stain.” and “Wood. Keep color. Add defects” were used. It seems that simply emphasizing the texture results in a color change in the wood’s texture. Although this color change disappears by increasing the value of “guidance”, the model also becomes overly aligned with the original image. Additionally, as the number of steps increases, the transformation makes the output more aligned with the input, but does not seem to add new defects. Instead, it highlights elements of the image that could already be seen as defects.

The most effective prompt found for further tests is: “Add defects. porosity. knot. crack. stain.” The results can be seen in Figures 8 and 9.

The results achieved with this model are promising at first glance. By balancing the “guidance” and the number of “inference steps”, it is possible to find points where the input images retain their structure, but with some defects applied. Selecting qualitatively, the points with $gui = 4|6|8$ and $steps = 50|100$ seem the most interesting. The higher the number of steps, the lower the intensity of the defects. The higher the guidance, the more defects are applied.

However, testing other prompts revealed that they have no effect on the anomalies added to the image when guidance values are very high. It appears that the algorithm naturally adds porosity and cracks to the wood during processing.

By lowering the guidance value, it was observed that the model does not understand what wood knots are, confusing them with rope knots made from wooden material. Furthermore, we are unable to generate paint stains on the texture. There is considerable room for improvement with possible fine-tuning of the model for industrial inspection.

Figure 8: Results with InstructPix2Pix for inference steps [20, 50, 100, 200] and guidance [3, 4, 6, 8].

Figure 9: Results with InstructPix2Pix for inference steps [20, 50, 100, 200] and guidance [3, 4, 6, 8].

4.2.3. *Stable-Zero123*

StabilityAI has released their model Stable Zero123 on HuggingFace, which applies rotational transformations to input images. Its functionality is similar to rendering 3D models, meaning that it seems to focus on generating new perspectives of objects captured in controlled environments or with segmented backgrounds. It does not appear to have been tested in scenarios with variable backgrounds.

The following results were obtained using the ComfyUI platform³. In Figure 10, results for different azimuth and elevation transformations of the camera can be observed. It tends to deform the input image – the whole

³<https://github.com/comfyanonymous/ComfyUI>

must be in the center of the object – as its topology seems to be non-trivial or unknown for the model. However, it keeps the color shift region mostly in place.

Figure 10: Data augmentation using AI-based rotation generation with StableZero123.

4.3. Experimentation with Ad-hoc Training

4.3.1. DreamBooth Training

This section explores the use of the DreamBooth technique for fine-tuning LLMs (in this case, the Stable Diffusion v1.5 model) with a few samples of a concept to teach the model to generate images of that concept. HuggingFace provides a simple tutorial for training⁴ and a best practices guide⁵.

In this case, the training set from the wood database will be associated with the prompt “a photo of wood moth repellent. white background”. It’s important to note that this is a text-to-image model, so the prompts provided are the only thing conditioning the model.

With DreamBooth, it’s crucial to adjust the hyperparameters carefully, as the model can easily overfit to the new samples. The hyperparameters used in two different tests are:

```
"instance_prompt": "a photo of wood moth repellent. white background"
"instance_data_dir": "data/squared" # Post-processed database with 600x600 square images
"pretrained_model_name_or_path": "runwayml/stable-diffusion-v1-5"
"resolution": 512
"train_batch_size": 2
"gradient_accumulation_steps": 1
```

⁴<https://huggingface.co/docs/diffusers/en/training/dreambooth>

⁵<https://huggingface.co/blog/dreambooth>

```
"learning_rate": 5e-06 and 1e-06
"lr_scheduler": "constant"
"lr_warmup_steps": 0
"max_train_steps": 400 and 800
"train_text_encoder": true
```

The results obtained with this configuration can be seen in Figure 11. Several transformations were made to the database to ensure the pieces appeared complete in the image. However, the model could not regenerate white backgrounds in these images, despite the prompt requesting it. Additionally, the generated pieces do not contain large areas with defects, although some small regions of the texture could be considered anomalous (see the center image of the figure on the left, where a black mark appears in the upper right). It's also worth noting that the placement of the central circle, the lighting, and even the object's geometry do not resemble what is found in the conditioning database.

In conclusion, this technique is positively evaluated for augmenting the wood database. Evaluated qualitatively, the textures seem to match those present in the database, and the fact that it generates different perspectives of the pieces can significantly enrich the variability in training set orientations. Its use is recommended for feature extraction data augmentation rather than for direct use in one-class classification tasks, as there is no guarantee that the generated images will be entirely free of anomalies.

Figure 11: DreamBooth technique results for Stable Diffusion v1.5 in two different experiments.

4.3.2. *AlignYourSteps (AYS) by NVIDIA*

A recent publication by NVIDIA⁶ proposes a methodology for fine-tuning the image inference process using DMs. The proposal only modifies a few lines of code related to the steps the generative AI model takes to transform noisy images into realistic final images. This publication argues that this technique can increase the level of detail in the generated images. The results can be observed in Figure 12.

(a) Experiment 1 without AYS

(b) Experiment 1 with AYS

(c) Experiment 2 without AYS

(d) Experiment 2 with AYS

Figure 12: AYS inclusion for the previous experiments.

⁶<https://research.nvidia.com/labs/toronto-ai/AlignYourSteps/>

4.3.3. Training from Scratch

In this section, we experiment with training a diffusion model from scratch to generate the wood database. This database contains 802 training images, which will be used to model the data distribution the diffusion model needs to learn. Unlike previously tested models, this one is not conditioned by anything. This means the images are generated purely from noise, thanks to the model learning the data distribution.

The implementation is based on the tutorial from HuggingFace⁷. The model was trained for 1000 epochs. Some of the generated images can be seen in Figure 13. As can be observed, the results from training a model from scratch are suboptimal compared to other techniques explored in this work. The textures of some images could match the expected wooden pattern. However, that is not the case of the majority of samples and the object’s geometry is deformed in most of the samples.

Figure 13: Results of training a diffusion model from scratch. These belong to epoch 629.

⁷https://huggingface.co/docs/diffusers/en/tutorials/basic_training

4.4. Conclusion

Among all the models tested, the combination of DreamBooth and AYS has proven to provide the best results, subjectively evaluated. This qualitative evaluation criteria combines how well the generated image matches the objects in the dataset and how varied the generated images are.

On the other hand, InstructPix2Pix has demonstrated the ability to introduce porosity defects (although the model does not seem to fully understand this type of defect) in the images from the wood moth dataset. Future work involves exploring fine-tuning of this model to enhance its knowledge in the field of industrial inspection, which is fairly limited in pre-trained models.

StableZero123 has shown to be a model capable of producing realistic perspective transformations on input images, which is a powerful tool for compensating for potential biases in the perspectives of the wood moth dataset (where control samples tend to appear more tangential, while anomalous samples appear flatter in relation to the camera).

Finally, training Diffusion Models (DMs) from scratch has been a costly process with limited benefits compared to the DreamBooth-based alternative.

5. Enhancing engagement and UX in serious games using LLMs: Emerging narratives and natural language interactions

5.1. Introduction

Serious games are those games that are not only conceived with a ludic purpose but also with a “serious” (learning, affecting behavior, promoting health, etc.) purpose in their core design [43, 44].

In both exclusive for-fun games and also serious games, implementing interactive narratives has long been a complex and challenging aspiration [45]. Traditional methods often rely on extensive scripting and predefined storylines, which can limit the flexibility and adaptability of the narrative to individual player actions. This rigidity may hinder the player’s sense of agency. Agency is the feeling of being in control of one’s actions and their consequences within the game world [46]. Crafting rich, interactive narratives is also resource-intensive, requiring significant time and effort from writers and developers to anticipate and script possible player interactions.

Interactive narratives play a crucial role in games by immersing players in a dynamic story that responds to their choices, thereby enhancing engagement. Engagement is another metric absolutely relevant for Game User

Experience (GUR) analysis. It represents the degree of attention, curiosity, and interest that players exhibit during the gameplay. In serious games, which are designed for purposes beyond mere entertainment, such as education, training, or behavior change, the importance of engagement is even more pronounced [47]. High levels of engagement can lead to better learning outcomes, increased motivation, and sustained interaction with the game content.

Agency and engagement are intertwined concepts in gaming. Agency refers to the capacity of players to make meaningful choices that affect the game’s outcome, contributing to a personalized experience [48]. When players perceive a high level of agency, they are more likely to become deeply engaged, as their actions have tangible impacts within the game world. This interplay fosters a temporary suspension of disbelief, allowing players to fully immerse themselves in the virtual environment and interact with synthetic characters as if they were real.

The integration of LLMs into game design presents both potential and challenges in generating emergent narratives, that is, stories that develop dynamically based on player interactions rather than following a predetermined script. LLMs can generate diverse and contextually appropriate responses, enabling more natural and varied interactions with non-player characters (NPCs). This capability can significantly enhance natural language interaction in games, allowing players to communicate with NPCs using everyday language rather than selecting from limited dialogue options.

However, incorporating LLMs into games also presents challenges. Ensuring the coherence and appropriateness of generated content is critical, particularly in serious games where the accuracy of information and alignment with educational or training objectives are essential. In addition, there are technical considerations related to integrating LLMs into game engines, managing computational resources, and maintaining real-time responsiveness.

This section explores the potential of leveraging LLMs to enhance engagement and UX in serious games through emergent narratives and natural language interactions. We examine the difficulties associated with the implementation of interactive narratives using traditional methods and how LLMs can address these challenges. Furthermore, we discuss the impact of enhanced engagement and agency on the effectiveness of serious games and outline strategies for integrating LLMs into game design while mitigating potential issues.

5.2. Previous works

The application of large language models (LLMs) in games has emerged as a transformative approach to enhancing interactive narratives and natural language interactions, thereby improving user engagement and experience. Advanced LLMs, such as OpenAI’s GPT-3 and GPT-4, have demonstrated remarkable proficiency in generating coherent and contextually appropriate text, making them ideal for dynamic storytelling and conversational interfaces within games.

An essential foundation for understanding the evolution of interactive narratives in games is the pioneering work of Chris Crawford. Crawford, a prominent game designer and author, has been a leading advocate for the development of interactive storytelling in games since the early days of the medium. His contributions have significantly influenced the way narratives are constructed and experienced in interactive media for the last 40 years.

In his seminal book, *Chris Crawford on Interactive Storytelling* [49], Crawford explores the complexities of creating narratives that respond dynamically to player input. He emphasizes that true interactivity in storytelling requires more than branching storylines; it necessitates systems where the narrative can adapt in real-time to the myriad choices a player might make. Crawford argues that the future of gaming lies in developing technologies and methodologies that allow for such fluid narrative experiences, moving beyond linear or pre-scripted paths.

One of Crawford’s notable projects is the development of the Storytron⁸ platform, an interactive storytelling engine designed to enable authors to create stories where characters and plots evolve based on player interactions [50]. Storytron aimed to model the intricacies of human social interactions and emotions, allowing for emergent narratives that are unique to each player’s experience. Although Storytron did not achieve widespread commercial success, it was a significant step toward realizing truly interactive narratives and highlighted the challenges inherent in such ambitious endeavors.

Crawford’s work is particularly relevant in the context of LLMs. The challenges he identified, such as creating believable characters, managing the combinatorial explosion of possible narrative paths, and maintaining narrative coherence, are areas where LLMs have shown considerable promise. Using the natural language understanding and generation capabilities of LLMs,

⁸<https://www.storytron.com/>

developers can address some of these challenges more effectively. For instance, LLMs can generate contextually appropriate dialogue for non-player characters (NPCs) on-the-fly, reducing the need for extensive scripting and enabling more organic interactions.

Recently, Park et al. introduced the concept of Generative Agents, which are LLM-powered entities capable of simulating human-like behavior in virtual environment [51]. These agents can remember past events, plan future actions, and interact with both the environment and other agents, resulting in complex social dynamics. This work aligns with Crawford’s vision of interactive narratives populated by characters with believable behaviors and motivations.

This emergent narrative could also be driven by conversational avatars, leading to significant improvements in user engagement and social presence, the feeling of interacting with sentient entities [52].

Traditionally, game dialogues were limited by pre-written choices, creating a rigid and often predictable interaction structure. With LLMs, however, NPCs can respond contextually to a wider variety of inputs, broadening the scope of player interaction and increasing immersion [21]. By embedding LLMs in Non-Playable Characters (NPCs), games are moving from pre-scripted dialogues to dynamic, player-driven conversations.

Players often report feeling more connected to NPCs because these models provide a semblance of personality and unpredictability, imitating the complexities of human interaction. This social presence is crucial for enhancing the realism of in-game environments, making the NPCs feel like real characters with whom players form relationships [53].

5.3. Implementation of LLMs in serious game: A practical example with Unity

Unity⁹ is the most widely used game development engine. In this section, an implementation of how to integrate LLM into the narrative pipeline is discussed.

The integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) into the Unity game development environment can substantially enhance interactive experiences by introducing sophisticated natural language capabilities. By enabling NPCs (non-playable characters) and other in-game systems to interact with players

⁹<https://unity.com/>

in an adaptive and contextual manner, developers can significantly increase narrative depth and player engagement. In this subsection, it will be detailed the process of integrating an LLM within Unity using a specialized script and .gguf files, a format specifically designed to facilitate efficient deployment of pre-trained LLMs.

5.3.1. *The LLM Class Implementation*

The LLM class is a foundational component for integrating a server-based LLM within Unity¹⁰. This C# class extends Unity's `MonoBehaviour`, allowing seamless integration into the Unity lifecycle. The class includes various properties and methods that provide developers with complete control over the LLM's configuration, performance, and runtime behavior.

The implementation features key aspects such as configuration parameters (port, numThreads, numGPULayers) to optimize server functionality according to the target hardware, ensuring flexibility for both local and remote environments.

The class offers a set of advanced methods for managing the underlying LLM model, including capabilities for configuring and modifying the model using LORA (Low-Rank Adaptation) adapters. Through methods like `SetLora()`, `AddLora()`, and `RemoveLora()`, the script supports runtime adaptation of the language model, making it suitable for diverse narrative scenarios where in-game NPC behavior may change based on player interactions or storyline progression.

A notable feature is the use of the `Awake()` method, which initializes the server asynchronously. By leveraging the `async` and `await` constructs in C#, the class ensures that model setup and loading processes do not impede the Unity main thread, thus preserving game performance and responsiveness.

5.3.2. *Leveraging .gguf Files for Efficient LLM Deployment*

The .gguf file format plays a critical role in the integration of LLMs within Unity, providing a highly optimized way to store and manage the parameters of large-scale pre-trained models. The .gguf format is specifically designed to address the challenges of deploying LLMs in real-time environments, making it well-suited for use in interactive game applications. This approach enables the possibility of adding new LLM by downloading and adding different .gguf files (see Figure 14).

¹⁰<https://github.com/undreamai/LLMUnity>

Figure 14: Loading new LLM from .gguf files

.gguf files are optimized for efficient loading, reducing the time required to initialize models during gameplay. This characteristic is crucial in game environments, where prolonged loading times can detract from the overall player experience. The cross-platform nature of .gguf ensures that the same model can be deployed across different operating systems, from high-performance servers to more constrained edge devices, without significant modifications.

One of the distinguishing features of .gguf files is their inherent support for GPU offloading. Within the LLM class, the numGPULayers property allows developers to determine the number of model layers to offload to the GPU. By specifying a higher value, developers can make optimal use of available GPU resources, thereby accelerating inference times and improving the responsiveness of NPC interactions. The .gguf format's compatibility with GPU-accelerated layers allows the model to be deployed in environments requiring real-time performance, such as fast-paced games where immediate responses are essential.

This format also includes extensive metadata, which allows for better management of the model lifecycle (see Figure 15). This metadata contains information about model architecture, hyperparameters, and versioning details, helping to ensure compatibility with different versions of loaders and deployment platforms. This flexibility is particularly important in a game development context, where multiple iterations and versions of a model may need to coexist, especially when models are continually refined or adapted.

Figure 15: GGUF file general structure. Source: HuggingFace <https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/gguf>

The workflow for integrating .gguf-based LLMs into Unity using the LLM class begins with specifying the model path using the SetModel() method. The .gguf file, containing the model weights, is stored in Unity's StreamingAssets folder, ensuring that the model is bundled with the game build and accessible at runtime. This ensures seamless access during both development and production phases.

The LLM class provides methods to further extend the model with LORA adapters stored in .gguf format. This feature is advantageous for personalization, allowing specific game characters to have individualized dialogue behavior by altering the underlying LLM in real time. The AddLora() and SetLoraWeight() methods, for example, facilitate the dynamic addition and adjustment of model components, enabling NPCs to adapt their responses

based on evolving game contexts or player behavior.

5.3.3. Real-Time Player Interaction and Server Management

A major advantage of using .gguf files in combination with the LLM class is the ability to maintain high performance during real-time interaction. The server management features of the LLM class—including threading, resource allocation, and GPU support—allow the LLM to run effectively without compromising game performance. By using the `llmThread`, the LLM operates independently of Unity’s main thread, ensuring that computationally heavy language generation tasks do not cause frame drops or lag, which is critical for maintaining a smooth player experience.

The integration of .gguf-based LLMs provides game developers with the tools to craft sophisticated, adaptive NPCs that interact in natural language, adding a significant level of immersion to the game environment. The use of properties such as `parallelPrompts` enables multiple LLM instances to handle concurrent requests, which is essential for multiplayer games where several NPCs may need to interact with different players at the same time.

To better illustrate this, a simple example in pseudo-code for this interaction is shown in Listing 1.

```
// Initialize the LLM instance to load a model in .gguf
// format
LLM mainLLM = new LLM()
// Set .gguf model path
mainLLM.SetModel("Assets/StreamingAssets/myModel.gguf")
mainLLM.numGPULayers = 30 // Use GPU layers
mainLLM.Awake() // Start server async

// Wait until the model setup is complete before proceeding
await mainLLM.WaitUntilReady()

// Set up the LLMCharacter instance, linking it to the
// initialized LLM
LLMCharacter npcCharacter = new LLMCharacter()
npcCharacter.llm = mainLLM // Link LLM instance
npcCharacter.playerName = "Player" // Set player name
npcCharacter.AIName = "GuideBot" // Set NPC name

// Load a specific personality for the NPC by setting the
// system prompt
npcCharacter.SetPrompt("You are a helpful guide for the
player, providing useful information about the game world.
")
```

```

// Player sends a query to the NPC
playerQuery = "Can you tell me about the history of this
place?"
npcResponse = await npcCharacter.Chat(playerQuery, callback =
    DisplayText)

// Display the NPC response in the game UI
DisplayText(npcResponse)

// Save the NPC's chat history to allow continuity between
sessions
await npcCharacter.Save("npcChatHistory")

// Load the saved chat history when the player re-engages
with the NPC
await npcCharacter.Load("npcChatHistory")

// Additional NPC interactions
playerQuery2 = "What's the main objective here?"
npcResponse2 = await npcCharacter.Chat(playerQuery2, callback
    = DisplayText)
DisplayText(npcResponse2)

// Adjust the NPC's personality by adding a LORA model file,
if needed
mainLLM.AddLora("Assets/StreamingAssets/npcPersonality.lora",
    weight = X)
npcCharacter.temperature = Y // Make responses more varied

// New player query after adjusting personality and
temperature
playerQuery3 = "What would you suggest for a beginner?"
npcResponse3 = await npcCharacter.Chat(playerQuery3, callback
    = DisplayText)
DisplayText(npcResponse3)

// Clean up resources when done
mainLLM.Destroy() // Stop and release the LLM server and
resources

```

Listing 1: Interaction example code.

5.3.4. Basic setup for NPCs

It is possible to define different conversational avatars with different personalities to assume different role-plays within a serious game.

In this testing environment, two avatars (AI1 and AI2 in Figure 16) are created with opposite personalities. This setup was only used for evaluation and never used in an actual context.

Figure 16: Basic setup for two conversational avatars

Each NPC should have a prompt to define its personality.

The prompts influence the responses of the NPCs. Interactions can be either text-based or voice-based, facilitated by various systems that enable Speech-to-Text (S2T) and Text-to-Speech (T2S) functionality in game engines like Unity.

5.3.5. Challenges and considerations

While .gguf files offer significant advantages for deploying LLMs within Unity, several challenges persist. The size of LLM models, even when stored in optimized formats like .gguf, can be substantial, which may impose memory constraints, particularly for games targeting devices with limited hardware resources. To address this, developers can utilize quantization features

Figure 17: Prompt for NPC number 1

Figure 18: Prompt for NPC number 2

available in .gguf files to reduce the storage footprint by employing lower precision data types (e.g., FP16 or INT8), albeit at the potential cost of a slight reduction in model accuracy.

Furthermore, while GPU offloading can greatly accelerate model inference, the benefits depend heavily on the GPU's capacity and architecture. Developers must carefully balance the number of layers offloaded to the GPU (numGPULayers) with the GPU's memory and processing capabilities to achieve optimal performance without risking out-of-memory errors. Another important factor is response time. Even when using local servers, the observed delay during testing ranges from 2 to 4 seconds, which is near the threshold for maintaining natural and fluid communication. This latency should be taken into consideration, and developers should strive to minimize response times. Additionally, any residual delay can be mitigated by leveraging narrative and gameplay elements to maintain immersion and distract players from response delays.

An alternative to GPUs could be TPUs (Tensor Processing Units), spe-

cialized hardware accelerators designed by Google to handle tensor operations in neural networks more efficiently. TPUs are particularly effective for large, complex models as they provide high throughput and lower latency, potentially reducing response times critical to fluid interactions. By leveraging TPUs, developers can achieve faster processing of neural network layers, helping to maintain real-time responsiveness and a seamless user experience.

5.4. Conclusions and further work

Conversational avatars as NPCs empowered by LLMs are an invaluable resource for serious games since they enable emergent narratives and personalized language interactions. Additionally, the possibility of customizing NPCs' personalities allows for more tailored and engaging player experiences. The collaboration between game developers, AI researchers, and domain experts could foster the development of specialized LLMs tailored to the unique requirements of serious games. This interdisciplinary approach may lead to innovative solutions that enhance both the technical and pedagogical aspects of serious game design.

Latency, even with locally served models, constitutes a major challenge that should be addressed because it's a key factor in ensuring natural conversations. While the integration of LLMs into serious games presents challenges, it also offers new opportunities to create more engaging, interactive, and personalized gaming experiences.

6. Using LLMs for Cost-Effective Demonstrations in Reinforcement Learning Environments

6.1. Introduction

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is a widely adopted approach for solving several decision-making problems across a variety of domains [54, 55, 56]. However, there are several scenarios where RL can be challenging: when the goal is abstract, when the desired behavior must mimic that of a human expert, when the environment is unstructured or continuously evolving, or when the design of the reward function is complex [57, 58, 22]. In such cases, Imitation Learning (IL), a subfield of RL, offers a compelling alternative. IL is particularly useful when the desired behavior is difficult to program directly. Instead of learning directly from scratch through trial and error like RL, IL allows agents to learn by observing expert demonstrations [59, 60]. In recent years, this field has gained attention for its potential applications,

such as in autonomous vehicles [61] or robotics [62]. In IL, the agent learns a policy by mapping observations to corresponding actions based on expert demonstrations, bypassing the need for carefully designed reward functions. However, obtaining these large expert demonstration datasets can often be costly or difficult, posing a significant challenge for IL [63].

One possible approach is using Large Language Models (LLMs) as a cost-effective method for generating expert demonstrations to facilitate IL. Existing research that uses LLMs to assist RL primarily focuses on tasks where a well-defined and complex reward function is available. For example, [59] proposes a framework where LLMs are used as policy priors to improve sample efficiency in RL, while [64] converts goals, histories, and observations into sequences processed by a policy initialized with a pre-trained LLM for sequential decision-making. Another approach [65], introduces the use of LLMs as a proxy reward function within RL frameworks. Furthermore, [66] introduces RoboCLIP, an IL algorithm that generates rewards for robot policies using a single video demonstration or textual description of the task, enhancing the training process in robotic environments. However, none of these works utilize LLMs to generate expert demonstrations. Our approach specifically leverages LLMs to create demonstrations for IL, enabling the agent to learn without relying on complex reward-based exploration. This is particularly valuable in environments where defining a robust reward function is challenging. By using IL, we can either simplify the reward function or even eliminate the need for a reward altogether, depending instead on expert demonstrations to guide the agent’s learning, making it more feasible to work in such environments. Moreover, IL techniques naturally incorporate classical RL methods, allowing the agent to refine its policy through further exploration after being initialized by LLM-generated demonstrations. The advantage of LLMs in this context lies in their ability to produce demonstrations that are accessible and low-cost, reducing the barrier to applying IL in complex scenarios.

In a typical RL loop, the agent receives observations from the environment, decides on the next action, executes it, and receives feedback through a reward system along with the updated state of the environment. This cycle continues as the agent gradually optimizes its behavior. However, for generating demonstrations in IL, the environment is often modified. Instead of allowing the agent to make its own decisions, a heuristic, a human expert, or an external system takes control. In our case, this heuristic is represented by an LLM. During the demonstration recording phase, the LLM receives

the current environment observation and determines the next action to execute as if it were a pre-trained expert agent. Once the demonstrations are collected, the standard RL environment is used for training the agent, where the agent uses the demonstrations to, among others, initialize the weights to avoid starting from nothing.

Although LLMs have shown great promise across various tasks [67, 68], often being considered a breakthrough solution, it’s essential to assess whether they are genuinely useful for generating demonstrations in the context of IL. Our goal is to evaluate the potential utility of LLMs in this specific setting, as their use introduces several challenges when an agent is guided by them: hallucinations, inaccuracies, and lack of contextual understanding, among others. Additionally, in this setup, LLMs do not learn or improve in real-time, so it is not a question of convergence. On the other hand, while standard RL can eventually solve tasks through exploration, it often requires a vast number of interactions, especially when rewards are sparse, making convergence slow and costly. By leveraging LLMs to generate initial demonstrations, we hypothesize that this approach could help RL models converge faster, provided the demonstrations are inexpensive to produce and of reasonable quality. The following sections will explore whether this strategy proves to be a viable and effective method.

6.2. Methodology and Experimental Setup

For the environments, we created custom RL scenarios using the Unity ML-Agents Toolkit¹¹. In Environment 1 (see Section 6.3), each environment step directly corresponds with a request-response cycle involving the LLM, rather than being tied to the standard `FixedUpdate` phase. This setup ensures that the demonstration step aligns with an RL training or inference step, maintaining consistency between the agent’s behavior during demonstration recording and its potential performance in traditional RL contexts. In Environment 2 (see Section 6.4), by contrast, a new action is only requested from the LLM when needed, allowing steps to synchronize with the `FixedUpdate` phase to apply the existential penalty during movement.

Given that the environment runs locally on our machine while the LLM is deployed on an external server with dedicated GPU resources, the communication between them is handled via WebSockets¹². Specifically, the Unity

¹¹<https://github.com/Unity-Technologies/ml-agents>

¹²https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/API/WebSockets_API

environment acts as the client and utilizes the `websocket-sharp` library¹³ to send observations to the server. On the server side, we run a Python-based WebSocket server using the `websockets` library¹⁴. The server is responsible for constructing the complete prompt using the received observations, processing it with the LLM, and then returning the next action to the Unity environment.

With respect to hardware and software, the Unity environment is run on a local machine equipped with an Intel Core i7-1360P CPU at 5 GHz, 32 GB of RAM, and Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS as the operating system, employing Unity version 2022.3.30f1 in conjunction with ML-Agents version 3.0.0-exp.1. The LLM, on the other hand, is deployed on a remote server featuring an Intel Xeon Icelake CPU at 2 GHz, 64 GB of RAM, and a dedicated NVIDIA A100 PCIe 80GB GPU, also running Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS. The server uses Python version 3.10.12 along with `websockets` version 12.

Regarding the LLM, we employ the `Meta Llama 3.1-8B-Instruct` model¹⁵, a state-of-the-art LLM developed by Meta and released in July 2024. This model is part of the Llama 3.1 family, optimized for multilingual dialogue tasks, and outperforms many available chat models on common industry benchmarks. We opted for the 8B version, which contains 8 billion parameters, as we expected it to be adequate enough for this task while maintaining a reasonable response speed.

Concerning the prompts, in each environment, we utilize two: one for the system role and one for the user role. The system role defines the general guidelines for how the LLM should behave, while the user role contains the current observation from the environment at each step and asks the LLM to generate the next action. It is important to note that no previous context is preserved between steps, i.e. for each interaction, the LLM only receives the system prompt and the current observation in the user prompt.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that we intentionally omit the agent training phase, as our primary focus is to evaluate the LLM’s effectiveness in generating cost-effective demonstrations with reasonable quality. This is because, given the simplicity of the proposed environments, the agent could learn rapidly through standard RL algorithms without the need for demon-

¹³<https://github.com/sta/websocket-sharp>

¹⁴<https://websockets.readthedocs.io>

¹⁵<https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct>

strations, making it difficult to measure the actual impact of the LLM on the agent’s learning process. Our study centers on how well the LLM achieves good rewards and/or minimizes the number of steps necessary to reach the desired outcome during the demonstration process.

6.3. Environment 1: Temperature Control

6.3.1. Description of the Environment

For the first environment, we designed a simple temperature control scenario. In this environment, a single agent is tasked with adjusting the room temperature where a user is located. Each episode begins by initializing the environment with the current room temperature, which is randomly set between 15 and 30 degrees Celsius, and a desired temperature, also randomly chosen between 15 and 30 degrees but different from the current temperature. Additionally, the user provides a natural language comment regarding their perception of the current room temperature. Figure 19 shows a visual representation of the environment.

Based on this comment, the agent must decide whether to increase or decrease the room temperature by 1 degree in each step. The environment concludes when the ideal temperature is achieved or when the maximum number of steps is reached. The reward structure is as follows: the agent receives a reward of +1 for reaching the ideal temperature, while it receives a reward of 0 otherwise.

The agent’s observation in the RL context consists of the current temperature and an embedding of the user’s comment. In contrast, the LLM only receives the user’s comment in natural language. The action space includes three possible actions: +1 (increase the temperature), -1 (decrease the temperature), or 0 (no change to the current temperature).

6.3.2. Prompts

Below, we present the system prompt utilized for the LLM and an example of a request and response. The text in black represents the static prompt that remains constant, while the text in blue denotes the current observation received from the environment.

Prompt for System Role:

You are responsible for adjusting the temperature of a house’s thermostat to ensure the comfort of its owner. The owner will provide feedback on how they feel regarding the current temperature, and based on this feedback, you must

Figure 19: Graphical representation of the temperature control environment, displaying the current room temperature (red background), the target temperature (blue background), and the user’s feedback (black background).

decide whether to increase, decrease, or maintain the temperature. Use this information to make informed adjustments and optimize the house’s temperature for comfort.

Prompt for User Role:

The feedback of the user is: “I am trying to relax, but the room feels colder than it usually does at this time.”. Provide the required temperature adjustment (+1, -1, or 0) to accommodate the user. Do not give explanations or justifications of any kind.

LLM Output:

+1

6.3.3. Results

We conducted a total of 1000 episodes, with each episode limited to a maximum of 20 steps. The average reward obtained was 0.81. Notably, although only 20 distinct user comments could appear, the LLM did not consistently make the same mistakes. For the same comment, the model could perform correctly in one episode but make an error in another. In general, we can say that the agent succeeded in adjusting the room temperature

to the desired level within the step limit on a high proportion of occasions.

6.4. Environment 2: Multi-Agent Forest Fire Extinction

6.4.1. Description of the Environment

In this environment, we designed a multi-agent environment simulating a forest fire scenario. The goal is to extinguish all active fires. The environment comprises F fires and A agents working collaboratively to extinguish all fires as quickly as possible. In our case, we have experimented with $A = 3$ and $F = 5$ or $F = 20$. At the start of each episode, the environment is initialized by randomly placing both the agents and the fires. Each agent must decide which active fire will suffocate and move towards it. The episode concludes when all the fires are extinguished or when the maximum number of steps is reached. A visual representation of one execution can be seen in Figure 20. The reward mechanism is local to each agent, meaning that an agent receives a reward of +1 for successfully extinguishing a fire, 0 otherwise, and an existential penalty of 0.001. There are no shared or global rewards in this scenario.

The agent’s observation for both RL and LLM contexts consists of its position, the position, and status (active or extinguished) of each of the five fires, and the other agents’ position and current target (if any). Based on this information, the agent must choose which of the five fires to move toward in an attempt to extinguish it. The action space is, therefore, limited to selecting one of the five fires as the next target.

6.4.2. Prompts

Below, we present the system prompt utilized for the LLM, along with an example of a request and response. As before, the text in black represents the constant static prompt, while the text in blue denotes the current observation received from the environment.

Prompt for System Role:

You are responsible for managing a team of three agents, each capable of putting out fires. A forest is currently on fire, with multiple hotspots scattered across the area. Your mission is to assign each agent to the closest fire, ensuring that no two agents are sent to the same location. All agents are equally capable, and each one can extinguish a fire on their own. You need to efficiently coordinate their movements to minimize the spread of the fire

Figure 20: Graphical representation of the forest fire environment, displaying the current active fires (red) and the agents (black) moving towards their corresponding assigned fires.

and optimize response time.

Prompt for User Role:

I am an agent whose mission is to extinguish the active fires. Several hotspots are currently burning, here are their IDs and coordinates:

- Fire_3 at (3.2,1.6)*
- Fire_2 at (13.7,6.9)*
- Fire_0 at (-1.3,7.9)*
- Fire_4 at (5.8,0.7)*

The information from the other helping agents is:

- Agent_1 is at position (6.5,8.4) extinguishing the fire with ID Fire_3*
- Agent_2 is at position (5.9,7.4) extinguishing the fire with ID Fire_2*

I am at position (2.9,8.6). Provide one ID of a fire that is not already assigned to another agent and is the closest to your own position. Do not give explanations or justifications of any kind. Example of output: Fire_3

LLM Output:

Fire_0

Figure 21: Comparison of the execution time to finish the task between the LLM and the random algorithm for two instance sizes, with 5 and 20 fires.

6.4.3. Results

In this case, we conducted a total of 100 episodes with a maximum of 2000 steps for two configurations: one using the LLM as the orchestrator of demonstrations and another using a Python script that receives a list of the active fires and selects one randomly. Additionally, we experimented with two instance sizes, with $F = 5$ and $F = 20$ active fires, and a fixed number of agents, $A = 3$, resulting in a total of four experiments. The results are presented in Figure 21. As observed, the LLM-driven approach generally performs better than the random selection method, with median values of 260 steps compared to 337 steps for the case of $F = 5$, and 620 steps compared to 779 steps for the case of $F = 20$.

6.5. Discussion

In the first environment, the temperature control scenario, the potential of the LLM to accurately interpret user intentions, even when expressed in varied forms, proved significant. It should be noted that, in this environment, the observation provided to the LLM differs from that of the RL agent: we can give to the LLM the user comment as raw text, but since RL observations must be represented as numeric vectors, the RL agent must receive an

embedding of the user’s comment. By leveraging the LLM’s understanding, the LLM demonstration initialization can significantly enhance the IL algorithm comprehension. For instance, if the embedding representation uses a Bag of Words model that includes terms like “cold” and “hot”, the algorithm can infer that the presence of “cold” should prompt an increase in temperature, and vice versa. Thus, this approach offers a compelling advantage over traditional methods, where initialization typically requires human feedback or extensive manual hardcoding with a large vocabulary. Based on the results, with an average accuracy of 81%, the LLM demonstrates its effectiveness in correctly interpreting the user’s intentions in most cases, making it a potential and simple approach to bootstrap the agent’s learning process.

In the second environment, the forest fire scenario, we deal with a multi-agent environment, which presents unique challenges when recording demonstrations. One of the key difficulties in such environments is the impracticality of manually controlling multiple agents simultaneously. A user could control one agent via keyboard to record demonstrations, but not all three simultaneously. While it might be possible to record demonstrations for one agent and apply the same policy to all three, this approach quickly becomes insufficient as the problem complexity increases, particularly when agents are assigned distinct roles (speciation). In such cases, each agent may require a specialized policy, making it challenging to rely on manual or single-policy demonstrations. Although the LLM operates as a black box and we cannot fully explain its decision-making process, it is interesting to evaluate its performance against a random baseline.

The results show that, while the performance improvement of the LLM over the random method is not dramatic, it consistently performs better in both scenarios. The difference in performance becomes more pronounced as the number of fires increases. With fewer fires, as in the $F = 5$ case, the random method has a higher probability of selecting an optimal target purely by chance. However, as the number of fires grows, as seen in the $F = 20$ case, the random selection becomes increasingly erratic, leading to greater inefficiency. This indicates that, even without a clear understanding of how the LLM arrives at its decisions, its guidance offers more structure than random actions, making it a useful tool for initializing agent behaviors. Additionally, while a program could be designed to calculate the closest fire not being extinguished, generating a prompt for the LLM is much simpler. Despite not being perfect, the LLM offers an effective initialization that, although suboptimal, is far easier to implement than custom logic or manual

control, providing a practical solution for this multi-agent scenario.

Across both environments, the LLM’s main strength lies in its ability to generate quick and easy demonstrations that can serve as a reasonable initialization for RL agents. This approach is particularly advantageous in situations where more sophisticated methods of obtaining demonstrations — such as manual coding or expert input— are too time-consuming or expensive. While these demonstrations may not be high-quality in the traditional sense, they provide a valuable starting point, helping the agent begin its learning process with some structure rather than relying purely on random exploration.

6.6. Conclusions and Future Work

In conclusion, the effectiveness of LLMs for recording demonstrations in IL depends on the specific context and user requirements. Their ability to process natural language makes them a convenient option in cases involving unstructured text, with the potential to work effectively in various scenarios. On the other hand, while a custom script may outperform an LLM in certain cases, especially when tailored for specific tasks, developing such a program often requires significant effort and expertise. LLMs offer a straightforward solution, particularly beneficial for users with less programming experience, such as designers, doctors, or domain experts. Although we cannot claim that LLMs are revolutionary in this domain, they present a viable alternative to complement traditional methods. While LLM-driven demonstrations are not designed to replace high-quality, expert-crafted demonstrations, they offer a cost-effective and accessible alternative that can significantly aid the initial stages of RL training.

As future work, several avenues can be explored. First, investigating new approaches to prompt design could enhance the quality and relevance of the responses generated by LLMs. Additionally, evaluating other LLMs optimized for providing concise answers, particularly in mathematical reasoning scenarios, may yield promising results. Furthermore, exploring multimodal approaches —where the LLM has access to visual representations of the environment— could improve response accuracy and context understanding.

7. Conclusion

Generative AI models, particularly LMMs and LLMs, present valuable opportunities to streamline and enhance complex tasks in various fields, from

industrial manufacturing to healthcare, gaming, and reinforcement learning.

In industrial anomaly detection, the experiments demonstrate that while generic VLMs perform well, they do not surpass specialized models like EfficienAD. However, combining these specialized models with VLMs can provide informed reasoning about detected defects. In clinical data augmentation, the incorporation of LLMs has enabled the creation of balanced datasets, with human oversight reinforcing the contextual quality of AI-generated augmentations. For synthetic image generation, DreamBooth-AYS demonstrated the best performance, InstructPix2Pix showed promising results for defect generation but when some fine-tuning is applied, and StableZero123 mostly resolved perspective challenges for small perspective variations. The application of LLMs in serious gaming has the potential to revolutionize player engagement, with conversational AI providing tailored and interactive experiences. However, latency issues remain a challenge, indicating that future work may need to address the balance between real-time interaction and model processing speed. Lastly, in reinforcement learning environments, LLM-driven demonstrations offer an accessible alternative to traditional approaches, particularly benefiting users with limited programming expertise. Yet, the effectiveness of these models in RL contexts can be further enhanced by refining prompt design and exploring multimodal strategies.

Overall, generative AI’s adaptability and robustness make it an ideal companion across fields, but the complexity of each domain often calls for hybrid methods and ongoing model customization. Future work across these applications should prioritize model fine-tuning, multimodal approaches, and interdisciplinary collaboration to fully realize the potential of generative AI.

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